

**COMPARISON OF CAREER CONFLICT IN DECISION MAKING
AMONG ADOLESCENTS**

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Abstract

The present study was aimed to analyse the difference in the career conflict of rural-urban adolescents and adolescents studying in government and private schools. It is assumed that the career conflict of rural and urban adolescents and adolescents studying in government and private schools does not differ significantly. Career-conflict scale by Kumar and Rekha (2015) was used for the data collection from 200 adolescents of 14-18 years. The findings of the study revealed that 24% urban adolescents shown low career conflict, 64% adolescents have average level of career conflict and 12% urban adolescents have showed high career conflict. 20% rural adolescents shown low career conflict, 56% adolescents have average level of career conflict and 24% rural adolescents have shown high career conflict. 23% adolescents studying in private schools shown low career conflict, 64% adolescents have average level of career conflict and 13% adolescents studying in private schools shown high career conflict. 21% adolescents studying in government schools shown low career conflict, 55% adolescents have shown average level of career conflict and 24% adolescents studying in government schools have shown high career conflict. The t-ratio of the career conflict scores of the adolescents belonging to urban and rural areas has not been found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence and 0.01 level of confidence. Similarly the t-ratio of the career conflict scores of the adolescents studying in private and government schools has not been found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence and 0.01 level of confidence.

Introduction

Career choice is one of the supreme significant decisions in an individual's life but, there are countable factors that put an influence on the career choice of the adolescents. These factors may include personal (self) and environmental factors, gender roles, academic background, peer pressure, parental influences, interest and many more which create conflicts for an adolescent to choose best suitable career. Amir & Gati (2006) explored that making career decisions is not an easy task. Indeed, career decision-making difficulties are among the most prevalent vocational problems of individuals.

Adolescence is that period of life when a student has to take fair decision of his/her vocational choices. It is a period of major turning in the life. The career will depend upon the subjects selected at this level. Choice of career is the most crucial stage for adolescents. Decision about career which is wrongly taken may badly effect the future life (physically and mentally) of adolescent.

In Chinese communities, the influence of family in career decision and career development is critical and career choices as well as work related issues are inseparable from relationships, especially in Asian communities (Young et. al., 2003). Abundant influences of family which consists of expectations of family, family support, family responsibilities and commitments, family as a safe in-group and friction between family on career decision making and shaping the values (Fouad et. al., 2008). These may come across in the way of career decision of adolescents.

The students studying in affluent schools are given advance training about their future career decision and to enter vocational college whereas in lower income school, career indecision is the norm (Ferry, 2006). According to Osakinle and Adegroye (2008), there are certain factors that influence adolescents' choice of career. These factors may include femininity and masculinity role, location and living conditions of adolescent, environment, school influence (peer, curricular content and school), religious affiliation, child rearing, and family values.

Studies have consistently revealed that high school and college students perceive a substantial number of barriers to career goal attainment, including ethnic and sex discrimination, financial problems, family attitudes, social support, perceived lack of ability, lack of fit, and lack of interest (Brown, et. al., 2012). Adolescents believe that the career-related barriers currently exist or that may be encountered in the future are not necessarily grounded in reality or based on factual information.

A number of social science scholars have investigated the influence of socio-economic status on the occupational/career decision of the youth. These studies consistently found that the socio-economic status of family has small but significant (Marjoribanks, 2002) to a large (Schoon & Parsons, 2002) effect on the career choices of the adolescents. These results have been found among the adolescents of Australia, diverse U.S. and British adolescents. Career decision making self-efficacy and choice anxiety do not differ significantly in relation to gender. Women reported to take more interest in taking requisite steps in order to achieve future goals and lower lack of readiness as compared to their counterparts (Walker & Tracey, 2012). There is a need to consider the role of future time perspective in adolescents' career development by psychologists, counsellors and teachers.

Career choice of adolescents involve the pursuit of rewards to be achieved in distant future such as being able to enter in a desirable career, earn a good livelihood, achieve independence and improve one's own competencies (Saunders & Fogarty, 2001). The decisions college students make invariably lead to important future vocational outcomes. However, some students tend to be more prepared to make career decisions than other students. Career choice of adolescents is influenced by many factors including personal, social and environmental factors which create conflicts for an adolescent to choose best suitable career.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explore the level of career conflict among adolescents belonging to rural and urban areas.
2. To explore the level of career conflict among adolescents studying in private and government schools.
3. To compare the career conflict among adolescents belonging to rural and urban areas.
4. To compare the career conflict among adolescents studying in private and government schools.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. No significance difference exists in the career conflict among adolescents belonging to rural and urban areas.
2. There is no significant difference in career conflict among adolescents studying in private and government schools.

Method and Procedure

The sample of the present study comprised of the adolescents who are in the age group of 14 to 18 years of Jalandhar, Kapurthala, Hoshiarpur and Nawanshehr districts of Punjab state of India. 200 adolescents from urban and rural background studying in government and private schools in the four districts were selected using stratified random sampling technique. 50 adolescents from each district were selected randomly. The present study was delimited to adolescents in the age group of 14-18 years of Jalandhar, Kapurthala, Nawanshahr and Hoshiarpur district of Punjab only.

Investigator used career-conflict scale (Kumar & Rekha, 2015) for the data collection. The scale consisted of 62 items. It was constructed and standardized by the investigators on 1024 adolescents and reliability of the scale was found to be 0.85. After the collection and tabulation of the data, the data was analyzed by applying mean, standard deviation, Significance of difference of statistics methods of statistics.

Results and Interpretation

1. Level of Career Conflict among Adolescents belonging to Rural and Urban areas

The first objective of the study was to explore the level of career conflict among urban and rural adolescents. The scores obtained from the 200 subjects on Career Conflict scale were calculated and compared with the z-score values provided in Career Conflict Scale (Kumar & Rekha, 2015). The results have been presented in the table 1

**Table 1
Level of Career Conflict among Adolescents belonging to Rural and Urban Areas**

Level of Career Conflict	Urban		Rural	
	N	Percentage	N	Percentage
Low Career Conflict	24	24%	20	20%
Average Career Conflict	64	64%	56	56%
High Career Conflict	12	12%	24	24%

It has been found that out of total sample of 100 urban adolescents 24% adolescents shown low level of career conflict, 64% adolescents have shown average level of career conflict, 12% adolescents showed high level of career conflict. Similarly, out of total sample of 100 rural adolescents 20% adolescents shown low level of career conflict, 56% adolescents have shown average level of career conflict and 24% rural adolescents have shown high level of career conflict.

2. Level of career conflict of adolescents Studying in Private and Government Schools

The second objective of the study was to explore the level of career conflict among adolescents studying in private and government schools. The scores obtained from the 200 subjects on Career Conflict scale were calculated and compared with the z-score values provided in Career Conflict Scale (Kumar & Rekha, 2015). The results have been presented in the table 1

**Table 2
Level of Career Conflict among Adolescents Studying in Private and Government Schools**

Level of Career Conflict	Pvt. Schools		Govt. Schools	
	N	Percentage	N	Percentage
Low Career Conflict	23	23	21	
Average Career Conflict	64	64	55	
High Career Conflict	13	13	24	

It has been found that out of total sample of 100 adolescents studying in private schools 23% adolescents have shown low level of career conflict, 64% adolescents have shown average level of career conflict and 13% adolescents studying in private schools have shown high level of career conflict. Similarly, out of total sample of 100 adolescents 21% adolescents shown low level of career conflict, 55% adolescents have shown average level of career conflict and 24% adolescents studying in government schools have shown high level of career conflict.

3. Difference in the Career Conflict of Adolescents belonging to Urban and Rural Areas

The third objective of the study was to compare the career conflict of adolescents belonging to rural and urban areas. To achieve this objective, the scores of Career Conflict Scale of adolescents belonging to rural and urban residential background were obtained and tabulated. Mean and SD values were calculated on the scores of their Career Conflict Scale which were found to be 227.84, 23.18 and 222.40, 18.15 respectively.

In order to analyse the significance of difference in the career conflict of adolescents belonging to rural and urban residential background, their career conflict scale scores were subjected to the calculation of t-ratio and the results have been presented in the table 3.

Table 3
Difference in the Career Conflict of Adolescents Belonging to Urban and Rural Areas

Sr. No.	Area	Mean	SD	df		t-ratio
1	Urban	$M_1=222.40$	18.15	100-1	198	1.84
2	Rural	$M_2=227.84$	23.18	100-1		

The results of the table 3 revealed that the t-ratio for the career conflict scores of the adolescents belonging to urban and rural areas has not been found significant at 0.05 level of confidence and 0.01 level of confidence. Thus, the hypothesis of the study which stated that no significance difference exists in the career conflict of adolescents belonging to rural and urban areas has been accepted. It could be interpreted from above discussion that there does not exist any significance differences in the career conflict of adolescents whether they are living in rural areas or in urban areas. To the best knowledge of the investigator, no study has been conducted on this variable. According to investigator, reason for no difference in the career conflict of rural and urban adolescents may be due to that the people in rural areas were now also getting latest information about different careers. Parents were providing full support to their children to pursue a career in their desired field. Facilities and guidance were being provided by the media, government and other organisations for higher studies and selection of appropriate career in rural areas as in the line of urban areas.

4. Difference in the Career Conflict of Adolescents Studying in Private and Government Schools

The fourth objective of the study was to compare the career conflict of adolescents studying in private and government schools. To achieve this objective, the scores of career conflict scale of adolescents studying in private and government schools were tabulated. Mean and SD values were calculated on the scores of Career Conflict Scale of adolescents studying in private and government schools which were found to be 223.72, 17.55 and 226.63, 23.95 respectively.

In order to analyse the significance of difference in the career conflict of adolescents studying in private and government schools, the scores of the career conflict scale of adolescents studying in private and government schools were subjected to the calculation of t-ratio and the results have been presented in the table 4.

Table 4

Difference in the Career Conflict of Adolescents Studying in Private and Government Schools

Type of School	Mean	SD	df		t-ratio
Private	$M_1=223.72$	17.55	100-1	198	0.97
Government	$M_2=226.63$	23.95	100-1		

The results of the table 4 revealed that the t-ratio for the career conflict scores of the adolescents studying in private and government schools has not been found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence and 0.01 level of confidence. Thus, fourth hypothesis of the study which stated that ‘There exists no significant difference in the level of career conflict of adolescents of government and private schools’ has been accepted. It could be interpreted from the above discussion that there does not exist any difference in the career conflicts of adolescents whether they are studying in government schools or private schools. To the best knowledge of the investigator, no study has been conducted on this variable According to the investigator; the reason behind this may be that the adolescents studying in private as well government schools are well aware about the different careers. Parents of adolescents are also aware of the different type of careers and they support their children to pursue a career of their own interest. Teachers also provide guidance to the students about different careers and motivate them to choose suitable career for them.

Conclusion

1. 24% urban adolescents shown low career conflict, 64% adolescents have average level of career conflict and 12% urban adolescents have showed high career conflict.
2. 20% rural adolescents shown low career conflict, 56% adolescents have average level of career conflict and 24% rural adolescents have shown high career conflict.
3. 23% adolescents studying in private schools shown low career conflict, 64% adolescents have average level of career conflict and 13% adolescents studying in private schools shown high career conflict.
4. 21% adolescents studying in government schools shown low career conflict, 55% adolescents have shown average level of career conflict and 24% adolescents studying in government schools have shown high career conflict.
5. The t-ratio for the career conflict scores of the adolescents belonging to urban and rural areas has not been found significant at 0.05 level of confidence and 0.01 level of confidence.
6. The t-ratio for the career conflict of scores of the adolescents studying in private and government schools has not been found significant at 0.05 level of confidence and 0.01 level of confidence.

References

Amir, T., & Gati, I. (2006). Facets of career decision-making difficulties. *British Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 34, 483-503

Amir, T., & Gati, I. (2006). Facets of career decision-making difficulties. *British Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 34, 483-503

Young, R. A., Valach, L., Ball, J., Turkel, H., & Wong, Y. S. (2003). The family career development project in Chinese Canadian families. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 62, 287-304

Fouad, N., Kantamneni, N., Smothers, M. K., Chen, Y. L., Fitzpatrick, M. E., Guillen, A. (2008). Asian American career development: A qualitative analysis. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 72, 43-59.

Ferry, M. Natalie (2006). Factors Influencing Career Choices of Adolescents and Youth Adults in Rural Pennsylvania. *Journal of Extension*. Vol. 44(3).

- Osakinle, E. O. and Adegrooye, B. S. (2008). *Vocational Guidance and Career Counselling*. Goldprints Publishers, Lagos Nigeria.
- Brown, S. D., Hacker, J., Abrams, M., Carr, A., Rector, C., Lamp, K., et al. (2012). Validation and measurement of a four factor model of career indecision. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 20(1), 3–21.
- Marjoribanks, K. (2002). Family contexts, individual characteristics, proximal settings, and adolescents' aspirations. *Psychological Reports*, 91, 769–779.
- Schoon, I., & Parsons, S. (2002). Teenage aspirations for future careers and occupational outcomes. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 60, 262–288.
- Walker, L.T. & Tracey, J.G. (2012). The role of future time perspective in career decision –making. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 81, 150-158.
- Saunders, R., & Fogarty, G. (2001). Time discounting in career preference. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 58, 118–126.